

Commentary on Ekashloki – Two-line summary of Advaita

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Summary:

Ekashloki is a famous two-line summary of Advaita. Advaita is the most difficult to understand philosophy which has ever been created. Most people struggle to understand what Advaita ever means. This two-line summary offers an unique chance to understand the most complex Advaita in the simplest possible language.

I present a simple word by word translation of the original Sanskrit and a commentary to help understand the entire meaning.

Discussion:

Here is the verse, word by word translation and commentary.

1) Verse:

किं ज्योतिस्तवभानुमानहनि मे रात्रौ प्रदीपादिकंस्यादेवं रविदीपदर्शनविधौ किं ज्योतिराख्याहि मे ।
चक्षुस्तस्य निमीलनादिसमये किं धीर्धियो दर्शनेकिं तत्राहमतो भवान्परमकं ज्योतिस्तदस्मि प्रभो ॥
इति श्रीमत्परमहंसपरिव्राजकाचार्यस्य श्रीगोविन्दभगवत्पूज्यपादशिष्यस्य श्रीमच्छङ्करभगवतः कृतौ
एकश्लोकी सम्पूर्णा ॥

2) Word by word translation:

Why (kim) (does) the light (jyothi) of your (tava) sun (bhanuman) during the day (ahani) become the inner light (pradeep) for me (me) during the night (rathrau); thus (evam) it is doubtful (syaath) (if) either (kim) perception (darshan) of the sun (ravi) or the inner light (deepa) is of the same form (vidhau) of light (jyothi), (please) inform (aakhyaahi) me (mey).

(When) at the time (samaye) those (tasya) eyes (chakshu) are closed (nimeelan), what (kim) is the intelligence (dhee) that is awareness (dhiya) in perception (darshane); what (kim) (is) out there (tatra) (is) myself (aham), therefore (atha) the light (jyothi) of you (bhavaan), O Supreme (paramakam) Lord (Prabhu), that (tath) I am (asmi).

Thus (iti), the text Ekashloki composed by (krthau) the glorious (shrimath), the highest realized (paramahansa), the wandering ascetic (parivrajak) and Acharya, the disciple of

(shikshasya) Pujya (honorable) Shri Govind Bhagavathpada, the glorious (shrimath) Shankara Bhagavatha (Adi Shankaracharya), is complete (sampurna).

3) Commentary:

Student: In the day time, I perceive the Sun shining outside me and giving rise to the day. Strangely, I also perceive a similar sun shining and giving rise to another day inside my dream when I close my eyes at night. I know the second experience is made up and unreal. I am confused as to the source of this light of the outer sun during daytime. Is it really an external source of light or is it also something deep within? Is the day experience also unreal. Can I know? How will I know?

It takes one to get out of the dream state to know it is unreal. Once, I get out of waking state, will I know that it also is not real?

Both day time and night time experiences are so alike when they are experienced, which makes everything even more puzzling. The real (waking state) and unreal (dream state) are so indistinguishable to the senses when they are experienced. On the contrary, all assumptions about our sense of reality could also be wrong. Is reality also unreal? Is there no reality at all in the end. Is reality unknowable?

Teacher: The light you perceive at night is intelligence that gives birth to awareness. The source of this intelligence and awareness belongs neither to your body nor to your mind, both of which are always in a state of change and decay. The source is much higher and deeper than the mind. It is deep within you when you extrapolate its existence. However, neither space nor time can bound it, it is beyond both.

This innermost self, which is beyond your body and mind, should be sought. This innermost self is the Atman. The light of the day (Brahman) is the light of the night (Atman). Since both are the same, the Brahman is of the nature of the Atman and the same as the highest Atman. The Atman is but a shard of the light of the Brahman. The highest Atman I can become is indistinguishable from the Brahman. Thus, whatever we call the highest form - Prabhu, Bhagavan, Ishvara, Brahman, or Paramatman, it lies deep inside me. Only a fool looks for divinity outside without realizing that it was inside him all the time.

4) Additional Commentary:

When one perceives the distant external world, it is typically through just two senses – sight and hearing. The other three senses need direct contact. To say that hearing and sight conveys every possible information about the external world is to attribute photons and sound waves with supernatural abilities. For a scientist, the entire external world can be said to be embodied inside photons and sound waves. How is that possible that the information of the entire universe can be located on photons and sound waves? This assumption is scientifically illogical. Nobody knows how the Newtonian and Quantum worlds interact with each other or if they are even capable of interacting. As far as scientists know today, these worlds have nothing similar to each other. Is not this assumption not the highest degree of logical incompetence. Sadly, tis is the state of affairs today. Nobody dares questions the assumptions made by modern scientists.

Let us go back to Ekashloki for another clue of the bizarreness of our everyday perception. One perceives space and time the same way in dreams as in one's waking life. This gives us a valuable insight. Space and time are not connected to the outside world. The modern scientific view is that we, as a part of nature, are enmeshed into the space-time fabric. This is a relative truth. The absolute truth that dreams reveal is that space and time are created by

something deep within us, it is above the brain and mind, both of which are prone to decay with age. This innermost self is the Atman. Let us examine how this question is typically answered by modern religion and modern science.

Response of religion: A philosopher like Berkeley would have said that the world outside one's immediate sensory perception exists because it is a mental creation of God. The critic would ask how Berkeley knew something he did know. How can anyone be 100% of the presence of an external entity? It is impossible. Berkeley was hinting at the external nature of the Brahman, but did not understand the inner nature of the Atman.

Response of Science: A scientist like Boltzmann proposed the idea of the Boltzmann brain whose brain gives to all perception in the universe it perceives. Nothing exists inside the world of the Boltzmann universe except the hallucinations of the brain. This is another simplistic idea that borders on solipsism. The Boltzmann brain idea hinges on one's mind being everything. By his own logic, a simple world would have been infinitely more possible to create than an infinitely complex world. The chances of a Boltzmann brain giving rise to an infinitely complex universe is infinitely low. However, we do see an infinitely complex universe. Hence, Boltzmann contradicts his own idea.

Why Advaita has a superior explanation?

Advaita solves the problem by positing two creators Atman of the inner universe and Brahman of the outer universe. The equivalency of the Atman and the Brahman is really of the Paramatman and the Brahman. For most seekers, the Atman they will discover is but a small shard of the light of the Paramatman (Brahman). Hence, complete equality is possible but improbable. Hence, Sri Ramanujacharya's version of Vishishta (relative) Advaita is closer to this work than the absolute Advaita typically attributed to Sri Adi Shanakaracharya's Advaita.